

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Cream for Management of Varicose Veins

Mamta Surve, Sakshi Kharate, Dr. S. Deshmukh

Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre, Washim - 444505.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 07 May 2026

Keywords:

Varicose veins, anti-inflammatory, manjishtha extract, guggul extract, olive oil, turmeric extract, aloe vera gel, anti-oxidant

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20063883

ABSTRACT

Varicose veins, a common vascular condition affecting a significant portion of the population, pose both cosmetic and medical concerns. Traditional treatment options often involve invasive procedures or synthetic medications, which may carry side effects. In this study, we aimed to formulate and evaluate a herbal cream as a non-invasive and potentially safer alternative for managing varicose veins. The herbal cream was developed using a combination of natural ingredients known for their anti-inflammatory, venotonic, and circulatory-enhancing properties including olive oil, manjishtha extract, guggul extract, turmeric extract and aloe vera gel. The formulated cream underwent comprehensive physicochemical characterization, including pH, viscosity, spreadability, and stability studies. Additionally, in vitro assay were conducted to assess the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of the cream. Preliminary results of this cream suggest promising outcomes, with the herbal cream demonstrating significant improvements in symptoms such as pain, swelling, and discoloration. further research is warranted to validate and explore the long-term effects and safety profile of the herbal cream as a potential alternative treatment for varicose veins.

INTRODUCTION

Varicose veins, characterized by dilated, tortuous veins often visible beneath the skin surface, represent a prevalent vascular condition affecting a substantial portion of the global population. While primarily considered a cosmetic concern, varicose veins can lead to discomfort, pain, and

complications such as venous ulcers and thrombosis, thereby impacting individuals' quality of life. Current treatment options typically involve invasive surgical procedures or the use of synthetic medications, which may be associated with adverse effects and limitations.

***Corresponding Author:** Mamta Surve

Address: Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre, Washim – 444505

Email ✉: mamtasurve21@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

In recent years, there has been growing interest in exploring natural remedies, particularly herbal formulations, as alternative treatments for various medical conditions, including varicose veins. Herbal remedies are often perceived as safer and more sustainable options, owing to their long history of traditional use and perceived lower risk of adverse effects compared to synthetic medications.

This study aims to contribute to the growing body of research on herbal treatments for varicose veins by formulating and evaluating herbal cream specifically designed for this purpose. The chosen herbal ingredients are selected based on their documented pharmacological activities, including anti-inflammatory, venotonic, and circulatory-enhancing properties. By harnessing the potential synergistic effects of these herbal constituents, the formulated cream aims to alleviate symptoms associated with varicose veins and improve overall vascular health.

In this paper, we describe the formulation process of the herbal cream, highlighting the selection and characterization of individual herbal ingredients, as well as the optimization of the formulation to ensure stability and efficacy. Furthermore, we present here *in vitro* assays investigating the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of the herbal cream, providing insights into its potential mechanisms of action. Finally, we discuss the design and methodology of a clinical trial conducted to evaluate the clinical efficacy of the herbal cream in patients with varicose veins. By employing a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study design, we aim to rigorously assess the effectiveness of the herbal cream in alleviating symptoms and improving quality of life in varicose vein patients.

Overall, this study seeks to contribute to the development of safe, effective, and accessible treatment options for varicose veins, while also

exploring the potential of herbal medicine in addressing vascular disorders.

VARICOSE VEINS

The word varicose comes from the Latin word "Varix", which means "twisted". According to WHO "The varicose vein may be defined as, "vein with a saccular development tortuous" The term "Varicosity" is generally employed to elongated, tortuous, pouched, thickened, friable vessels, inelastic which have constantly lost its valvular efficiency through analogous changes may also occur in veins. Chronic Venous Insufficiency of the lower limb is the ailment which involves some indications and symptoms take place because of venous hypertension. The modern system tries to develop the immune mechanism in the blood system by resorting to the antitoxic substances in the blood stream, but with no assurance of permanent cure. Ayurveda advocates, "Let the noxious blood be let out". It will either cure the disease or else it will make a clear pathway towards further treatment modalities.

The symptoms which show in patients such as :

- Prominent leg veins
- Muscle cramps
- Discoloration
- Pain
- Itching
- Heaviness
- Venous Ulceration

Causes:

Weak or damaged valves can lead to varicose veins. Arteries carry blood from the heart to the rest of the body. Veins return blood from the rest of the body to the heart. To return blood to the heart, the veins in the legs must work against gravity.

Muscles tighten in the lower legs to act as pumps. Vein walls help blood return to the heart. Tiny valves in the veins open as blood flows toward the heart, then close to stop blood from flowing backward. If these valves are weak or damaged,

blood can flow backward and pool in the veins, causing the veins to stretch or twist.

HERBAL CREAM

Cream and herbal cosmetics has been an increasing demand for herbal medicine, also called botanical medicine or phytomedicine prepared by using any plant's seeds, berries, roots, leaves, bark, or flowers for medicinal purposes. Long practiced outside of conventional medicine, herbalism is becoming more main stream as up to-date analysis and research show their value in the treatment and prevention of disease. Recently, the World Health Organization estimated that 80% of people worldwide rely on herbal medicines for some aspect of their primary health care. Plant drugs are frequently considered to be less toxic and freer from side effects than the synthetic ones. Along with other dosage forms, herbal drugs are also formulated in the form of ointment and creams I have developed a very easy method of herbal antiseptic cream Herbal antiseptic cream is a shooting cream enriched with nature it is valuable gift of nature and their demand is increasing in the world market. The herbal antiseptic cream is very effective cream It have no side effect. Antiseptic Cream is a soothing cream enriched with nature's goodness, which accelerates the healing of injured skin. The ingredients in the cream help in healing irritable rashes, sores, eruptions, prickly heat, and mild skin infection.

Key Features of Herbal Cream

1. Herbal creams typically boast natural ingredients like plant extracts, essential oils, and vitamins.
2. They're favored for their gentle, nourishing properties, often used for skincare, soothing irritations, and promoting healing.
3. Common features include hydration, anti-inflammatory effects, and antioxidants, catering to various skin types and concerns.

Advantages of Herbal Cream

- **Natural Ingredients:** Herbal creams typically contain natural ingredients derived from plants, herbs, and botanical extracts, which can be beneficial for the skin and may have fewer adverse effects compared to synthetic alternatives.
- **Gentle on the Skin:** Many herbal creams are formulated to be gentle on the skin, making them suitable for individuals with sensitive skin or those prone to allergies or irritation.
- **Minimal Chemicals:** Herbal creams often have fewer synthetic chemicals, preservatives, and artificial fragrances compared to conventional skincare products, reducing the risk of adverse reactions or long term skin damage.
- **Potential Therapeutic Benefits:** Certain herbs used in herbal creams may possess therapeutic properties such as anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, or soothing effects, which can help improve various skin conditions or promote overall skin health.
- **Customizable Formulations:** Herbal creams can be customized to target specific skin concerns or conditions by selecting herbs and botanicals known for their beneficial properties, allowing for personalized skincare solutions.

MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY

Material

1. **Aloe Vera gel** : Acts as the primary base; provides hydration, soothing effect, and helps heal irritated skin.
2. **Beeswax** : Serves as a thickening agent and consistency builder; also forms a protective barrier on the skin
3. **Borax** : Acts as a co-emulsifier; helps mix oil (olive oil, beeswax) and water (aloe, distilled water) into a stable cream.
4. **Manjishtha extract** : Functions as a skin brightening and detoxifying agent; helps improve complexion and reduce pigmentation.

5. Turmeric extract : Acts as an anti-inflammatory and antibacterial agent; useful for acne, redness, and skin glow.

6.Guggul extract : Provides anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects; supports acne control and skin repair.

7.Methyl paraben : Used as a preservative; prevents microbial growth and increases shelf life of the cream.

8.Peppermint Oil : Fragrance agent Acts as a natural fragrance, giving the cream a fresh, minty smell.

9.Olive oil : Works as an emollient; softens and nourishes the skin, prevents dryness.

10.Distilled water : Functions as a solvent and diluent; helps dissolve water-soluble ingredients and adjust the cream's consistency.

Preparation of cream

1. Heat liquid paraffin and beeswax in a borosilicate glass beaker at 75 °C and maintain that heating temperature (Oil phase).

2. In another beaker, dissolve borax, methyl paraben in distilled water and heat this beaker to 75 °C to dissolve borax and methyl paraben and to get a clear solution. (Aqueous phase).

3. Then slowly add this aqueous phase to heated oily phase.

4. Then add a measured amount of aloe Vera gel, Guggul extract, Manjishtha extract and Turmeric extract and stir vigorously until it forms a smooth cream.

5. Then add few drops of peppermint oil as a fragrance.

Formulation of cream

Methodology

Table .No 1: Formulation Table

SR.NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	Guggulu extract	1.5ml	2.5ml	2.5ml
2	Manjishtha extract	1ml	1.2ml	2.5ml
3	Turmeric extract	0.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml
4	Olive oil	10ml	15ml	13ml
5	Aloe Vera gel	1.5ml	2.5ml	2.5ml
6	Beeswax	3gm	3.5gm	4gm
7	Borax	0.2gm	0.3gm	0.3gm
8	Methyl paraben	0.02gm	0.04gm	0.06gm
9	Peppermint oil	0.08ml	0.06ml	0.04ml
10	Distilled water	2.2ml	3.5ml	3.6ml

EVALUATION PARAMETER

Procedure of Evaluation Of Cream

1. Physical evaluation: In this test, the cream was observed for colour, odour, texture, state.

2. Washability: A small amount of cream was applied on the hand and it is then washed with tap water.

Before Applied

After Applied

Fig.No.1- Washability Test

3. pH: 0.5 g cream was taken and dispersed in 50 ml distilled water and then PH was measured by using digital PH meter.

Fig.No.2-pH Measurement

4. Phase separation: Prepared cream was kept in a closed container at a temperature of 25- 100 °C away from light. Then phase separation was checked for 24 h for 30 d. Any change in the phase separation was observed / checked.

5. Irritancy: Mark the area (1 cm²) on the left-hand dorsal surface. Then the cream was applied to that area and the time was noted. Then it is checked for irritancy for an interval up to 24 h and reported.

Before Applied

After Applied

Fig.No.3- Irritancy

Test

6. Greasiness: Here the cream was applied on the skin surface in the form of smear and checked if the smear was oily or grease-like.

7. Homogeneity- A good cream formulation should be homogeneous in nature. It implies proper mixing and compatibility of the constituents. We checked the homogeneity of our cream by visual appearance and by touch. The cream was homogeneous and smooth to touch.

8. Spreadability: The spreadability was expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from the cream, placed in between the slides, under certain load. Lesser the time taken for separation of the two slides better the spreadability. Two sets of glass slides of standard dimension were taken. Then one slide of suitable dimension was taken and the cream formulation was placed on that slide. Then other slide was placed on the top of the formulation. Then a weight

or certain load was placed on the upper slide so that the cream between the two slides was pressed uniformly to form a thin layer. Then the weight was removed and excess of formulation adhering to the slides was scrapped off. The upper slide was allowed to slip off freely by the force of weight tied to it. The time taken by the upper slide to slip off was noted. Spread ability = $m \times l/t$

Where,

m = Standard weight which is tied to or placed over the upper slide (30g)

l = length of a glass slide (5 cm)

t = time taken in seconds.

Fig.No. 4-Spreadability Test

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

SR. NO.	EVALUATION PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3
1	Physical evaluation a. Colour b. Odour c. Texture d. State	o Faint yellow o Mild herbal o Smooth o Semi-solid	o Faint yellow o Mild herbal o Smooth o Semi-solid	o Faint yellow o Mild herbal o Smooth o Semi-solid
2	Irritancy	slight adverse effect observed	No adverse effect observed	No adverse effect observed
3	Wash-ability	Hard to washable	Easily washable	Easily washable
4	pH	7.9	6.80	6.91
5	Spread-ability (g x cm/sec)	22.8	22.5	21.6
6	Phase separation	No phase separation	No phase separation	No phase separation
7	Greasiness	Non greasy	Non greasy	Non greasy
8	Homogeneity	Uniform distribution Non greasy of extract	Uniform distribution Non greasy of extract	Uniform distribution Non greasy of extract

Test for steroid :

TEST	PROCEDURE	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Salkowski test	Guggul Extract + Chloroform + Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Reddish Brown Colour	Presence of Steroid

Test for polyphenol :

TEST	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1. Extract + Sulphuric acid	Crimson Colour	Curcumin is Present
2. Extract + Boric acid	Reddish brown colour	Curcumin is Present
3. Extract + 1ml Hydrochloric acid	Pink colour	Curcumin is Present
4. Extract + Ferric chloride	Green colour	Curcumin is Present

Evaluation parameter for Herbal Cream:

DISCUSSION

The formulation and evaluation of a herbal cream for the management of varicose veins utilizing ingredients such as guggul, Manjishta, turmeric, olive oil, and aloe vera gel offer promising potential due to their known therapeutic properties.

Guggul, known for its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties, could help alleviate the pain and inflammation associated with varicose veins. Manjishta, a herb traditionally used in Ayurvedic medicine for its blood purifying and anti-inflammatory effects, may aid in improving blood circulation and reducing swelling. Turmeric, with its potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, could further contribute to reducing inflammation and preventing oxidative damage to the blood vessels.

Olive oil's moisturizing and emollient properties could provide a soothing effect on the skin, potentially relieving discomfort and dryness often experienced with varicose veins. Aloe vera gel, renowned for its cooling and healing properties, may help soothe irritated skin and promote tissue repair.

In terms of evaluation, various parameters need to be considered such as stability, pH, viscosity, spreadability, skin irritation potential, and efficacy in relieving symptoms associated with varicose veins. Clinical trials would be necessary to assess the cream's effectiveness in reducing pain, swelling, and improving overall vascular health.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

Summary

The herbal cream formulated for managing varicose veins contains guggul, Manjishta, turmeric, olive oil, and aloe vera gel. These ingredients are chosen for their potential to alleviate symptoms associated with varicose veins, such as inflammation and poor circulation. Guggul is known for its anti-inflammatory properties,

Manjishta helps improve blood circulation, turmeric offers antioxidant benefits, olive oil nourishes the skin, and aloe vera gel soothes and moisturizes. The cream is designed to be applied topically to affected areas. Its efficacy can be evaluated through clinical trials assessing its ability to reduce swelling, pain, and improve the appearance of varicose veins over time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the formulation and evaluation of a herbal cream for managing varicose veins utilizing olive oil, guggul, manjishtha, turmeric, and aloe vera present a promising avenue for natural and effective treatment.

By combining the moisturizing properties of olive oil with the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant benefits of guggul, manjishtha, turmeric, and aloe vera, the cream offers a holistic approach to alleviating symptoms associated with varicose veins, such as pain, swelling, and discomfort.

Through rigorous evaluation encompassing physical properties, stability, safety, efficacy, user feedback, and regulatory compliance, the cream can be fine-tuned to ensure both safety and efficacy. This process may involve adjustments to ingredient ratios, incorporation of additional active ingredients, or optimization of formulation techniques.

Ultimately, the development of a herbal cream for varicose vein management holds the potential to provide individuals with a natural and accessible solution to improve their vascular health and overall well-being. Further research and clinical studies will be valuable in validating its effectiveness and broadening its accessibility to those in need.

REFERENCES

1. Thida Ching, Justin A Roake, David R Lewis, Net-based information on varicose vein

- treatments: a tangled web, *Journal of the New Zealand Medical Association*, NZMJ 24 September 2010, Vol 123 No 1323; ISSN 1175 8716 for 2. Bhatia, A., et al. Metabolic profiling of *Commiphora wightii* (guggul) reveals a potential source pharmaceuticals and nutraceuticals.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2014.12.016> *Phytochemistry* (2015),
2. Monika Shekhawat and S. S. Sisodia, A Review on pharmacology of oleo-gum resin of *commiphorawightii*, *World journal of pharmaceutical research*, Volume 10, issue 13, 723-835
 3. Dr. Nidhi Garg and Dr. Akhil Jain, Ayurvedic perspective of varicose veins, *World journal of pharmaceutical research*, Volume 6, issue 3, 296-310
 4. Poonam Dang, Sakshi Badyal, Puneet Dhawan, H. S. Tiwari. Apex herbs in the management of varicose vein - A boon to contemporary treatment. *Jour. of Ayurveda & Holistic Medicine*, Vol.-XI, Issue-X (Oct. 2023).
 5. Jaiganesh Kandasamy Palanisamy, Sivakumar Ponnu, Sivasankar Mani and Sreedharren Balakrishnan, A critical review on traditional herbal drugs : an emerging alternative drug for varicose veins, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Vol 7, Issue 05, 2018, 316-338
 6. Dhyan et al., Formulation and Evaluation of Multipurpose Herbal Cream, *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*. 2019; 9(2):341-343
 7. Ratha KK, Aswani PS, Dighe DP, Rao MM, Meher SK, Panda AK. Management of Venous Ulcer through Ayurveda: A Case Report. *J.Res Ayurvedic Sci* 2018;2(3):202-208.
 8. Protiva Talukdar, Shivani A C, Prasanna Narasimha Rao. Integrated approach towards management of venous ulcer with Nimba Tila Kalka: a case report. *Jour. of Ayurveda & Holistic Medicine*, Vol.- XI, Issue-V (May 2023).
 9. Akshay Suden,, Management Of Varicose Veins : An Ayurvedic Review, *IRJAY*, September: 2020 Vol- 3, Issue-9; 1-28; Doi: <https://doi.org/10.47223/IRJAY.2020.3919>
 10. Meenakshi Priyadarshni, L.N. Shukla, Herbal Treatment of Hemorrhoids: An Ayurvedic Method, *International Journal of Indigenous Medicinal Plants*, ISSN: 2051-4263, Vol., Issue1
 11. Evare et al., Clinical study of dashang guggul in the management of midoroga, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Vol 11, Issue 13, 2022.
 12. Dharmendra Dubey, Prashant K. and S.K. Jain, In-vitro antioxidant activity of the ethyl acetate extract of gum guggul (*Commiphora mukul*), *Biological Forum – An International Journal*, 1(1): 32-35 (2009)
 13. Rohit Singh, Astbhuja Mishra, Ramanand Prajapati and T. Narender, Method development for isolation and purification of Z-Guggulsterone, Dihydroguggulsterone, and Progesterone from guggul resin using RP-HPLC, *A Platinum Open Access Journal for Organic Chemistry, Arkivoc* 2023 (vi) 202211902
 14. Kajal U. Kamble and Dr. Sachin A. Nitave, A Review on varicose veins and its treatments, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Vol 11, Issue 5, 2022, 678-689
 15. Santosh V. Gandhi, Nikita M. Nigar and Mangesh R. Bhalekar, Formulation and evaluation of phytoconstituents cream for the treatment of Varicose veins, *World journal of pharmaceutical research*, vol 7, issue 12, 732-745
 16. Nataliya Ionescu (BORDAI), Andreea-Miruna Neagu, Marina popesc. Preparation and characterization of vegetable oils and

- plant extract with effect in the treatment of Varicose veins, *U.P.B.sci.Bull.,series B vol 83 issue 3*, 2021, 1454-2331
17. PariharS,SaraswatiChattarpal,SharmaD,Abri efreviewonherbsuseinthetreatmentofVaricose veins, *Journal of drug delivery and therapeutic* 2022, 12(1) ,158-162
 18. Girish D. Dahikar, Dipika D. Giradkar, Shagufta A. Khan and Rajendra O. Ganjivale, A review on remedies use in the treatment of Varicose veins and veriocele, *GSC biological and pharmaceutical science*, 2022, 18(02), 244-252
 19. Tatjana Kundakovic, Marina Milenkovic, Sasa Zlatkovic, Vesna Nikolic, Goran Nikolic, Ivana Binic,Treatment of venous ulcers with the herbal based ointment herbadermal : A perspective non- randomized study, *forschkomplementmed* 2012, 19: 26-30
 20. Ivana Binic, Aleksandar Jankovic, Milan Miladinovic, Forde Gocev, Dimitrije Jankovic and ZoralVrucinic, Evaluation of healing effects of new herbal formulation on venous leg ulcer: pilot study, *Actaedicamedianae*, 2011, 50(2): 39-42
- Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Cream For Management of Varicos.

HOW TO CITE: Mamta Surve, Sakshi Kharate, Dr. S. Deshmukh, Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Cream for Management of Varicose Veins, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 1339-1347, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20063883>

